

Crop management

Performance of late transplanted rice in Assam

L. Saikia, K. Chandra, and T. C. Mahanta, Assam Agricultural University, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), Titabar 785630, India

We tested rice varieties against CNM539 in a trial conducted in two agroclimatic

conditions at RARS in Titabar and North Lakhimpur during 1987 wet season. Five transplanting dates ranged from 10 Aug to 20 Sep, at 10-d intervals, with 30-d-old seedlings used for the first 2 dates and 50-d-old seedlings for the last 3 dates. Spacing was 20 cm × 15 cm, with 4-6 seedlings/ hill. Fertilizer was applied basal at 40-20-20 kg NPK/ ha.

At Titabar, all varieties exhibited better grain yields with 30-d-old

seedlings (see table). At North Lakhimpur, yields also were better with 30-d-old seedlings; 50-d-old seedlings transplanted 10 Sep also had higher yields. While panicle number/m² differed with transplanting date, panicle weight was consistent.

Delayed planting up to 10 Sep did not result in much reduction in panicle number, panicle weight, and grain yield in any of the varieties tested. □

Performance of late-transplanted rice in Assam.

Planting date	Grain yield (t/ha)									
	Titabar					North Lakhimpur				
	KMJ-1-52-3	Andrew Sali	CNM539	IET725	Mean	Saragphola	Solpona	Manoharsali	CNM539	Mean
10 Aug	4.8	4.2	4.2	3.3	4.2	3.6	3.6	4.0	4.8	4.0
20 Aug	4.8	5.9	5.4	4.9	5.2	3.6	3.5	4.1	4.2	3.9
31 Aug	4.6	5.0	4.9	4.3	4.7	3.7	3.7	4.2	4.3	4.0
10 Sep	3.6	3.9	4.5	2.9	3.7	3.7	3.7	4.4	4.4	4.0
20 Sep	—	—	—	—	—	3.2	3.2	3.4	3.2	3.3
Mean	4.4	4.8	4.7	3.8	—	3.6	3.5	4.2	4.0	—
LSD (0.05)	For variety	0.1				Variety	ns			
	For date	0.4				Date	0.5			

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Response of flooded rice to zincated urea and zinc sulfate

O. Muñiz, R. Beltran, H. Irigoyen, N. Arozarena, and N. Viera, Agrochemistry Department, Soil Institute, Apartado 8022, Boyeros, Havana, Cuba

We studied the effect on rice yield of Zn applied as zincated urea and zinc sulfate to flooded rice soils during the 1987 wet season. Two experiments were conducted: a pot experiment using dry seeded rice variety J-104 and a Gley Yellowish soil (clay loam, with pH 7.2, 2.19% organic matter, 48-116 ppm PK (Oniani), and 1.40 ppm Zn extracted with N NH₄Ac pH 4.8), and a field experiment using dry seeded rice variety

IR880 and a Gley Ferrallitic soil (sandy, with pH 6.8, 2.40% organic matter, 35-215 ppm PK, and 1.80 ppm Zn). Four treatments were studied in each trial, in a randomized block design with four replications.

In treatment 1, fertilizer was applied at 187 kg N as urea (68 basal + 68 at tillering + 51 at panicle initiation), 40 kg P as concentrated superphosphate, 50 kg K/ ha as potassium chloride in the pot experiment, and 119 kg N (34 + 51 + 34), 51 kg P, and 51 kg K/ ha in the field experiment (control). Treatment 2 had control fertilizer rates but used Cuban-produced zincated urea (41% N and 3% Zn) for the first 2 N fractions, for a total Zn application of 18 ppm Zn in the pot experiment and 6.2 kg Zn/ ha

Effect of zincated urea and zinc sulfate on rice yield. ^a Havana, Cuba, 1987 wet season.

Treatment	Grain yield	
	g/pot	t/ha
No Zn	12.23 b	3.6 c
Zincated urea	18.00 a	6.8 a
Zn sulfate 1	14.37 ab	5.6 b
Zn sulfate 2	14.27 ab	6.2 ab

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly (P<0.05) by DMRT.

in the field experiment. Treatment 3 had control fertilizer rates plus soil zinc-sulfate (22% Zn) at the same Zn rate as in treatment 2. Treatment 4 had control fertilizer rates plus soil zinc sulfate basal at double the rate.

Grain yields increased significantly with Zn (see table). □